

ORGANIZATION THE INDEPENDENT WORK OF STUDENTS IN GENERAL PHYSICS UNDER CONDITIONS OF DEVELOPMENTAL EDUCATION (*USING THE EXAMPLE OF TEACHING THE SECTION “OPTICS”*)

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Abstract. *Physical – scientific basic of technics. So learning physics, learners introduce with the goals of natural phenomena’s and their scientific interpretation. This article deals with the facilities of formation of abilities and skills of future physics teachers and use of these skills in the teaching process. Also consider the questions of activation of teaching process, improving the effectiveness of lessons which is necessary in then future career.*

Keywords: *professional skill, development, formation, quality of education, creative ability.*

Introduction

One of the serious problems related to higher education reforms is increasing the competitiveness of graduates in the labor market and ensuring that the education they receive meets modern requirements. The current era of modernization of the entire education system imposes higher demands on the professional training of subject teachers, significantly changing and complicating the role of educators in universities. Now, a teacher is not only a source of information but also a person who organizes and manages the educational process, facilitates the developmental learning of students, and possesses the necessary knowledge and culture that allow them to independently solve pedagogical and methodological tasks constantly arising in their professional activities.

The current system of teaching physics in most universities consists of lectures, practical sessions, and laboratory work. The learning process concludes with an exam. Let us take a closer look at what practical sessions typically involve in a university. During practical sessions, the teacher initially briefly repeats what was already covered in the lecture. Then, they demonstrate how to solve a certain problem. This takes up half of the session. Students diligently take notes, fighting off sleep. At the end, they are offered to solve one or two problems of the same type.

It is worth focusing separately on the exam. What does a standard exam look like? The student takes a question card and goes to prepare. The main task of preparation is to copy answers to pre-known questions from pre-prepared cheat sheets. So, the crisis is evident. What should be done?

Methodology

What kind of methodological training should a physics teacher have to effectively solve the tasks assigned to them during the implementation of the modern educational process and the technologization of physics education? Nowadays, practically everyone understands that the most promising solution to emerging problems is the technologization of the educational process — that

is, equipping the teacher's work with pedagogical technologies. Scientists, relying on general theoretical principles, engage in the scientific development of specific pedagogical technologies that, in their opinion, should assist teachers in solving certain specific methodological problems.

We consider technological training as the process of forming special integrative professional qualities in a teacher, mastering theoretical and practical mechanisms, and acquiring the necessary experience of new activities that determine the teacher's readiness to create and apply personalized pedagogical technologies based on their subjective experience.

At the same time, methodological training and technological training should constitute a unified system, both in content and in the essential professional sense, representing the final stage of teacher (specialist or master's degree) preparation. Modern society places high demands on specialists with higher education, including teachers. Society needs a new type of teacher who possesses not only subject knowledge but also methodological knowledge, as well as methods and techniques of cognitive activity. The latter allow solving the problem of forming and developing students' cognitive independence.

Significant contributions to the theory and practice of developing students' independence in the learning process have been made by the research of M.I. Makhmutov, P.I. Pidkasisty, and A.V. Usova. It should be noted that research by methodologists in the field of theory and practice of independent work continues. As a result, the theory is enriched with new provisions and facts. However, alongside this, certain difficulties are observed in solving some issues. For example, there is no unified interpretation of the concept of "independent work." One reason for differing opinions on this concept is that some authors classify independent work as a teaching method, others view it as a form of organizing lessons, others as a type of learning activity, and still others as a means of instruction.

Analyzing the results of students' independent activity, we found that they predominantly exhibit reproductive thinking processes, practically lacking the ability to analyze and generalize material or to apply scientific methods in practice. Most of them are unable to independently and creatively acquire knowledge.

Setting the task of developing a methodology for organizing students' independent work, we started from the premise that the entire educational process should be oriented toward students' independent cognitive activity, the formation of scientific methods of cognition as ways of acquiring new knowledge, and the development of reflection. At the same time, the following authorial definition of independent work is given:

"Independent work is a type of learning defined by students' ability to consciously set tasks and goals, plan their activity, implement it, carry out self-monitoring, and reflect." Considering that each element characterizing such activity is formed and developed in the learning process, independent work should be viewed as a layered concept: reproductive, productive, and creative work.

Based on the research results, a methodological system for organizing students' independent work has been improved (Table 1).

This methodological system encompasses the methodological foundation, the paradigm of the educational process, didactic goals and principles, educational content, teaching tools, methods, forms, applied innovative technologies, and standard as well as non-standard academic and test assignments that enable assessment of students' level of formation of a physical worldview and the effectiveness of the process.

Table 1

Methodical System for Organizing Students' Independent Work

№	Components of the Methodical System	Specific Features of the Component
1	Methodological Basis	Principles of the International Assessment System
2	Paradigm of the Educational Process	Student-centered individualized, differentiated education, competency-based approach
3	Identified Goals	Shaping learning objectives of students' independent work assignments according to Bloom's taxonomy
4	Didactic Principles	Scientific approach, unity of theory and practice, systematicity, logical sequence, visual aids, clarity, consistency
5	Educational Content	Theoretical knowledge, practical skills, application abilities, foundational and physical competencies within the subject of "Physics"
6	Teaching Tools	Natural-visual and verbal demonstration tools, hypermedia educational and informational programs
7	Teaching Methods	Reproductive, problem-based, logical, independent work, self-monitoring, and evaluation methods
8	Forms of Teaching	Lessons, excursions, laboratory work, practical work, extracurricular activities, clubs
9	Innovative Technologies	Problem-based learning, working in small groups, collaborative learning, and project-based technologies
10	Control and Self	Monitoring - Standard and non-standard academic and independent work assignments

Results and discussion

One of the most important qualities of a teacher is their ability to organize interaction with students, communicate with them, and guide their activities. A teacher's professional mastery is determined by the level of development of a range of pedagogical and methodological skills, which is the key goal of the entire student training system in higher education institutions. The effectiveness of any activity organized by a teacher, whether during a lesson or beyond, depends not only on the thoughtful choice of subject-specific technologies but also on the ability to manage emotional contact with students and creatively build a system of pedagogically appropriate relationships [2, 61].

Modern pedagogical literature notes that the highest result of environmental education is the cultivation of ecological culture in students — that is, the formation of an understanding of how humans should interact with nature and what consequences can arise from ill-considered

interference with its laws. “Ecological culture” is a relatively new issue, which has sharply come to the forefront due to humanity’s close approach to a global environmental crisis. The relentless technical progress we often discuss in lessons has brought humanity to a survival situation, and the future fate of generations will depend on ecological consciousness and the ecological culture of people.

Under modern conditions, scientific comprehension and development of practical approaches to fostering students’ ecological culture have become especially important, constituting one of the key directions in the work of educational institutions. The goal of ecological education in lessons is to cultivate a responsible attitude toward the environment in students, to nurture individuals ready for practical activity, promotion of ecological ideas, and protection and improvement of the environment.

Solving physics problems is one of the most important means of developing the thinking and creative abilities of future physics teachers. Often, problem situations in lessons are created through tasks, which in turn activate the cognitive activity of future physics teachers.

We observed the work of students who had the opportunity to stay in the physics laboratory to carry out their ideas for conducting various experiments not only during class days but whenever the lab was free. Their enthusiasm is hard to overestimate. Practice shows that student experimenters, striving to understand the causes of the physical phenomena observed in their experiments, work very carefully with the textbook text. They explained the experiments independently, which helps develop the student’s monologic speech associated with the comprehension of the presented knowledge. After all, if knowledge is not the product of the student’s own activity but merely the result of memory work, then mastering it remains formal [1, 195].

The work on forming skills during the training of students in the methodology of teaching physics should be based on the general structure of skills, taking into account the specifics of communicative skills. A significant number of students experience serious difficulties during teaching practice in managing students’ learning activities under explanatory-reproductive, problem-based, developmental, and other types of teaching and in organizing communications appropriate to these types of instruction.

The quality of a student’s education depends on what and how they are able to do to manage their creative self-development and improve the quality of their training as a future teacher. Self-organization and self-planning of one’s activities are essential components of a teacher’s creative self-development. They provide the future specialist with the ability to consciously design themselves and bring changes in their physical, mental, moral, aesthetic, and other aspects.

Creative self-development of a person is inconceivable without self-control and self-assessment of the results of educational activities, reflection on cognitive actions, thought processes, and one’s potential abilities. Self-assessment and reflection allow one to identify successes and gaps in self-improvement and creative self-development. They enable the teacher to keep a finger on the pulse of their creative self-development, to control and manage their progress towards self-improvement, which helps the teacher learn to manage themselves and achieve unity with their own self [3, 40].

Conclusion

Thus, the question of how to teach physics today remains largely debatable. There are many possible answers to it, but hardly any can be considered solely correct and indisputable. However, it is undoubtedly true that effective learning of physics is possible only when the teacher organizes

such forms of work that are called active and that are capable of engaging students and stimulating the learning process.

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